

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

This study is motivated by the social dynamics arising from entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach, Bandengan Village, Jepara Regency, which have triggered local community complaints concerning noise, traffic congestion, waste accumulation, and concerns over potential shifts in social and cultural values. These conditions require the Bandengan Village Government to develop adaptive communication strategies to balance the economic benefits of tourism with the comfort and order of local residents. The aim of this research is to analyze the communication strategies implemented by the village government in responding to community complaints, including their effectiveness, challenges, and broader implications. This study employs a qualitative descriptive approach with a case study design, utilizing in-depth interviews, participatory observation, and document analysis. The findings indicate that the village government applies dialogical and participatory communication strategies through village meetings, policy socialization, the use of both conventional and digital media, and the development of persuasive and empathetic messages. These strategies have proven effective in reducing potential conflicts and fostering public trust, although several obstacles remain, such as limited human resources, unequal access to information, and differing interests among stakeholders. The study emphasizes that strategic communication plays a crucial role as an instrument for social harmony, public participation, and sustainable village development. The results are expected to provide practical recommendations for village governments and tourism managers facing similar social dynamics.

Keywords: *communication strategy, village government, community complaints, tourism, Tirta Samudra Beach*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism has become one of the strategic sectors in local economic development, particularly in coastal areas with high natural and cultural potential (Muchammad Satrio Wibowo & Belia, 2023). One example is Tirta Samudra Beach, located in Bandengan Village, Jepara Regency, Central Java. This beach is widely recognized as a leading tourist destination that not only offers attractive natural scenery but also various entertainment activities that draw visitors from both within and outside the region. Entertainment activities organized in the coastal area, such as music performances, cultural festivals, recreational rides, and community events, serve as a distinctive attraction as well as a form of utilizing local potential to improve community welfare. According to Juniasa (2020), the village government, together with local tourism actors, has leveraged these activities to increase village-generated revenue, encourage the growth of the creative economy, and introduce local culture to a broader audience.

According to Wiyanto (2011), amid the rapid development of the tourism sector, various social dynamics have emerged that require serious attention. One prominent issue is the increasing number of complaints from local residents regarding entertainment activities that are perceived to disrupt environmental comfort and public order. These complaints include noise from music performances that continue late into the night, traffic congestion around access roads to the beach, unmanaged waste accumulation, and the potential for environmental degradation due to the lack of sustainable management. In addition, local communities have expressed concerns about the erosion of social and cultural values as a result of external influences that may not align with the norms upheld by the Bandengan Village community. Communication strategy serves as an important instrument that can be utilized by the village government in addressing community complaints. According to Iman and Rahmat (2020), a communication strategy refers to systematic and integrated communication planning directed toward achieving

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

specific objectives (Sumarlan et al., 2025). In the context of village governance, communication strategies function as tools for creating dialogue spaces, building trust, and channeling community aspirations. As stated by Hamsa Ramadhan et al. (2022), communication is no longer viewed as a one-way process in which the government merely disseminates information, but rather as a two-way or even multi-directional process that enables the exchange of ideas, deliberation, and collaboration (Rafi & Sumarlan, 2025; Sumarlan & Anis, 2025). According to Amantha (2021), village governments have a dual role in managing tourism areas. On one hand, they seek to optimize tourism potential to increase village-generated revenue and enhance community welfare. On the other hand, they are responsible for maintaining public order, social comfort, and prevailing social values. In responding to community complaints regarding entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach, the village government needs to implement adaptive and contextual communication strategies. As noted by Mustanir et al. (2018), one effective strategy is the regular organization of village deliberation meetings involving community members, tourism actors, and other relevant stakeholders. Village deliberation forums serve as important platforms for disseminating information, listening to public aspirations, and reaching agreements on measures to be taken in managing entertainment activities.

According to Rahartri (2019), the use of communication media is also a crucial aspect of village government communication strategies. Currently, social media platforms, residents' WhatsApp groups, village information boards, and local radio broadcasts can serve as effective channels for disseminating information and managing public opinion. These media enable faster, broader, and more interactive information dissemination. As stated by Putra Perssela et al. (2022), communication media play a significant role in shaping public perceptions of an issue. Therefore, village governments must be able to manage public communication effectively, particularly in conveying policies, regulations, and public appeals related to entertainment activities in tourist areas. From a development communication perspective, the role of village governments in creating effective communication is crucial to the success of social development at the local level. According to Krisnanti et al. (2022), development communication should position the community as subjects rather than merely objects of development. This means that communities have the right to be involved in decision-making processes related to their living environment, including the management of tourism areas. As argued by Hastrida and Hendriyani (2023), dialogic communication is expected to foster mutual understanding among village governments, communities, and tourism actors, thereby enabling the alignment of diverse interests.

This study focuses on the communication strategies employed by the Government of Bandengan Village in responding to community complaints regarding entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach. According to Safitri and Mujahid (2024), by examining the communication patterns applied, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of communication strategies, the obstacles encountered, and the solutions implemented in the communication process. The findings of this study are expected to offer practical recommendations for village governments and other tourism villages in managing tourism activities more prudently, thereby maintaining a balance between economic interests, community comfort, and environmental sustainability. Therefore, the title of this research is "The Communication Strategy of the Government of Bandengan Village, Jepara Regency, in Addressing Community Complaints Regarding Entertainment Activities at Tirta Samudra Beach."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on village government communication strategies has been widely conducted, although each study highlights different aspects. Amantha (2021) emphasizes the important role of village governments in improving community welfare through face-to-face communication, particularly village deliberation meetings as the primary medium of interaction. In line with this, Hastrida and Hendriyani (2023) introduce a dialogic communication perspective, which is considered effective in fostering social harmony in community-based tourism management. Meanwhile, Alfiyah (2023) underscores deliberation as a participatory space, while noting that studies on the utilization of digital media in the context of village governance remain relatively limited. From the perspective of participatory communication, Nida (2014) offers another viewpoint by emphasizing the role of persuasion in mass communication media as an important instrument in shaping public opinion. This perspective is reinforced by Safitri and Mujahid (2024), who highlight the effectiveness of communication strategies within organizations, demonstrating that systematic communication planning can enhance message acceptance and strengthen relationships between institutions and their publics. Although these studies make valuable contributions to enriching the understanding of communication strategies at both village and organizational levels, relatively few have specifically focused on village government communication strategies in responding to community complaints arising from entertainment activities in tourism areas. This research gap is important to address, as social dynamics in tourism

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

regions are not only related to economic aspects but also to issues of comfort, public order, and the sustainability of local socio-cultural values. As a conceptual foundation, this study adopts the communication strategy theory proposed by Cangara Hafied (2020). This theory conceptualizes communication strategy as a systematic planning process consisting of five key components: determining communication objectives, audience analysis, message formulation, media selection, and evaluation. Through this framework, the study is able to comprehensively analyze the effectiveness of village government communication strategies within the context of local social and cultural dynamics. Therefore, this research is expected not only to contribute to the expansion of the literature on communication strategies at the village level but also to provide practical recommendations for managing public communication in the context of community-based tourism.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This study employs a descriptive qualitative approach with a case study design. This approach was chosen because it allows for an in-depth understanding of the communication dynamics carried out by the Government of Bandengan Village in responding to community complaints regarding entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach (Rusandi & Muhammad Rusli, 2021). The research subjects include officials of the Bandengan Village Government, community leaders, tourism actors, and residents living around the coastal area who are directly involved in or affected by entertainment activities. According to Ardiansyah et al. (2023), data were collected through in-depth interviews with key informants, participatory observation of village deliberation forums and other public communication activities, as well as documentation studies consisting of village policy archives, meeting minutes, and related media publications. The collected data were analyzed using the interactive analysis model proposed by Miles and Huberman (1994), which consists of three stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. To ensure data validity, this study applied source and method triangulation by comparing data obtained from interviews, observations, and documentation, thereby ensuring that the findings are more objective and academically accountable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The research findings indicate that entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach constitute a central issue in the social dynamics of Bandengan Village. On the one hand, these activities support the local economy by providing employment opportunities for residents and increasing village-generated revenue. However, according to Ahmad Sunaryo and Imam Rosidi (2020), significant complaints have emerged from the community, highlighting issues such as noise pollution, traffic congestion, waste accumulation, and concerns regarding the potential erosion of local cultural values. These complaints are generally conveyed through various channels, including village deliberation forums, community leaders, and communication media such as residents' WhatsApp groups. The Government of Bandengan Village has responded to these complaints by implementing dialogic and participatory communication strategies. These strategies are realized through village deliberation forums, policy socialization activities, the use of social media, and the formulation of persuasive messages. Based on the analysis, the communication strategies implemented by the village government can be categorized as relatively effective in

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

mitigating potential conflicts between residents and entertainment business actors. Nevertheless, this effectiveness has not been evenly distributed, as several obstacles persist, including limited resources, disparities in access to information, and fluctuating levels of public trust. The communication strategies adopted by the village government demonstrate a considerable level of effectiveness in reducing conflict potential and enhancing public trust, although their impact remains uneven. According to Bayu (2022), communication messages are designed to be persuasive, clear, and empathetic, emphasizing a balance between tourism interests and social comfort. The village government does not merely convey regulations but also highlights social, health, and environmental impacts, thereby constructing messages that are both motivational and capable of fostering collective awareness. Audience analysis conducted by the village government has been a key factor in the success of this strategy, as communication is tailored to the characteristics of a heterogeneous audience. This includes elderly residents who prefer face-to-face communication, younger generations who are more active in digital media, and tourism actors who are primarily oriented toward economic considerations.

Table 1. Interview Data

No.	Position	Descriptions
1	Village Head	Direction of village policies related to entertainment activities, decision-making processes, and efforts to maintain a balance between tourism development and community comfort.
2	Village Secretary	Administrative coordination, documentation of deliberation outcomes, and preparation of official reports related to community complaints and policy follow-up actions.
3	Village Officials (Hamlet Head / Neighborhood Leaders)	Direct dissemination of information to residents, channeling aspirations related to noise, traffic congestion, and waste management, as well as supervising the implementation of regulations at the neighborhood level.
4	Village Consultative Body (BPD)	Policy oversight functions, provision of critical input, and representation of community voices in village governance through village deliberation forums.
5	Community Leaders and Religious Leaders	Preservation of local social and cultural values, provision of moral legitimacy for policies, and encouragement of community compliance through cultural and religious approaches.
6	Village Youth	Utilization of social media to express aspirations, involvement in managing entertainment events, and participation in maintaining order and cleanliness in tourism areas.
7	Entertainment Tourism Business Actors	Agreements regarding entertainment operating hours, responsibility for waste management, contributions to the village economy, and roles in maintaining a safe and comfortable tourism environment.

As noted by Cangara Hafied (2020), audience analysis indicates that the village government's communication strategy takes audience heterogeneity into account. Local communities are divided into groups with different communication preferences: elderly groups value face-to-face communication through deliberation forums, while younger generations respond more positively to messages delivered through digital media. According to Budhi Pamungkas Gautama et al. (2020), tourism and entertainment business actors tend to prioritize economic aspects, prompting communication messages to emphasize a balance between financial benefits and social responsibility. Community leaders also play a strategic role as opinion leaders who help disseminate government messages and provide moral legitimacy in the eyes of the public. Audience analysis thus becomes a critical determinant of communication strategy effectiveness.

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

The communication messages formulated by the village government prioritize persuasive, clear, and empathetic principles. For instance, when communicating regulations regarding nighttime entertainment restrictions, the village government does not solely emphasize regulatory aspects but also explains the impact of noise on residents' comfort and public health. Messages are conveyed using simple and easily understood language and include appeals for maintaining collective order. Informative messages are combined with motivational messages, with the village government frequently emphasizing that entertainment activities serve as a means of tourism promotion while also requiring social responsibility. Through this approach, communication messages function not merely as instructions but as tools for building collective awareness.

The village government's communication media combine conventional and modern approaches. According to Syarifuddin and Utari (2022), conventional media such as mosque loudspeakers, village information boards, and face-to-face communication are effective in reaching elderly residents who are relatively less active in digital media. Meanwhile, according to Cahyono (2016), social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram are utilized to disseminate information to younger audiences and tourists. Residents' WhatsApp groups function as rapid communication channels when sudden complaints arise or announcements related to entertainment activities need to be conveyed. Facebook and Instagram, on the other hand, are used to disseminate official village information and to shape positive public opinion regarding the government's efforts to maintain a balance between tourism development and community comfort. This diverse media selection demonstrates the village government's awareness of the importance of aligning communication channels with audience characteristics.

According to Rahma et al. (2023), communication evaluation is another aspect that receives attention from the village government. Evaluation is conducted through both formal and informal mechanisms. Formally, evaluation is reflected in village meetings and deliberation reports that document the number of complaints, responses, and follow-up actions taken. Informally, evaluation is carried out by monitoring public opinion through social media and daily interactions within the community. The data indicate that the number of complaints tends to decrease following the consistent implementation of communication strategies, although some community members still perceive government follow-up actions as slow or inconsistent. This finding suggests that effective public communication must be accompanied by concrete policy implementation to avoid generating public distrust.

Several supporting factors contribute to the success of the communication strategy, including the strong deliberation culture in Bandengan Village, high levels of community participation in communication forums, the use of digital media to expand information reach, and the village government's commitment to following up on community aspirations. The culture of deliberation, in particular, serves as social capital that facilitates constructive dialogue. However, several inhibiting factors were also identified, such as limited public communication skills among village officials, disparities in access to information due to unequal digital capabilities, fluctuating levels of public trust, and conflicting economic interests between entertainment actors and residents who prioritize environmental order.

From a theoretical perspective, as articulated by Cangara Hafied (2020), the findings of this study reinforce the relevance of communication strategy theory, which emphasizes five main components: goal determination, audience analysis, message formulation, media selection, and evaluation. These five components have proven applicable in the context of village governance and are effective in explaining how communication strategies can reduce social conflict at the local level. This study also supports the concept of development communication that positions communities as subjects rather than objects of development. Through deliberation forums and dialogic communication, communities are not merely recipients of policy but are positioned as partners in the formulation of collective solutions.

Practically, the findings of this study offer several important implications. First, village governments need to strengthen the communication capacity of village officials through training in public communication, conflict management, and digital technology utilization. Second, community complaint systems should be formalized through complaint posts or transparent and accountable digital applications. Third, village governments should develop integrated policies that emphasize not only the economic aspects of tourism but also social comfort and environmental sustainability. Fourth, the dialogic communication model implemented in Bandengan Village can serve as a reference for other tourism villages facing similar challenges. The findings also indicate that the success of the village government's communication strategy is largely supported by deliberation forums and face-to-face communication deeply embedded in local culture. According to Nadia (2023), new challenges arise in the digital era, where negative opinions can spread rapidly through social media and trigger collective dissatisfaction. Future communication strategies must therefore strengthen responsive and interactive digital communication. Village governments must not only disseminate information but also respond quickly and transparently to public questions,

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

criticisms, and complaints. Moreover, the success of communication strategies is highly dependent on the consistency of policy follow-up, as communication that is not accompanied by tangible implementation risks generating greater public disappointment. This study confirms that the communication strategy of the Government of Bandengan Village plays a crucial role in maintaining a balance between tourism-related economic interests, community comfort, and environmental sustainability. Through a combination of participatory communication, the utilization of conventional and digital media, and persuasive and empathetic messaging, the village government has been able to reduce conflict escalation and enhance public trust. Despite existing limitations, the communication strategy implemented has provided a positive direction for the more prudent and sustainable management of entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the communication strategy implemented by the Government of Bandengan Village in responding to community complaints regarding entertainment activities at Tirta Samudra Beach plays an important role in creating a balance between tourism interests and social comfort. According to Firmansyah et al. (2023), through participatory village deliberation forums, the village government has been able to open inclusive spaces for dialogue, accommodate community aspirations, and build collective consensus regarding policy decisions. The use of conventional and digital media in the communication strategy reflects the adaptability of the Government of Bandengan Village to a heterogeneous audience in terms of age, social background, and preferences in receiving information. Messages delivered through persuasive and empathetic approaches have been proven to foster emotional closeness and increase public trust in village policies. Nevertheless, this study identifies several challenges that still require serious attention, including the limited capacity of village officials in managing public communication, disparities in access to information due to differences in digital literacy, and differing interests among stakeholders that have the potential to create new dynamics in tourism management. Overall, these findings affirm that strategic communication functions not only as a means of information delivery, but also as an important instrument in maintaining social harmony, strengthening community participation, and directing village development toward a more inclusive, adaptive, and sustainable approach.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that the Government of Bandengan Village strengthen more systematic public communication mechanisms by prioritizing the reinforcement of village deliberation forums and the development of transparent and accountable digital-based complaint systems. Consistency in policy implementation is a key factor in maintaining and strengthening public trust, ensuring that decisions generated through participatory processes can be implemented in a tangible and sustainable manner. Furthermore, enhancing the capacity of village officials should be given priority, particularly in terms of public communication skills, the utilization of digital technology, and conflict management capabilities, so that village authorities are able to respond more adaptively to social dynamics. Community participation also needs to be expanded inclusively by involving youth, women, and marginalized groups, so that the decisions taken truly reflect the interests of all segments of society. Through these measures, the communication strategy of the Government of Bandengan Village is expected to become increasingly responsive, adaptive, and inclusive in maintaining a balance between tourism interests, social comfort, and environmental sustainability in the Tirta Samudra Beach area.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad Sunaryo, & Imam Rosidi. (2020). Efektifitas Media Website Dalam Peningkatan Pelayanan Publik. *J-KIs: Jurnal Komunikasi Islam*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.53429/j-kis.v1i2.186>
- Alfiyah, A. (2023). Musyawarah Berdaya Komunikasi. *Alamtara: Jurnal Komunikasi Dan Penyiaran Islam*, 7(2). <https://doi.org/10.58518/alamtara.v7i2.2273>
- Amantha, G. K. (2021). Peran Pemerintah Desa Dalam Meningkatkan Kesejahteraan Masyarakat. *Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan Widya Praja*, 47(1), 67–79. <https://doi.org/10.33701/jipwp.v47i1.1490>
- Ardiansyah, Risnita, & Jailani, M. S. (2023). Teknik Pengumpulan Data Dan Instrumen Penelitian Ilmiah Pendidikan Pada Pendekatan Kualitatif dan Kuantitatif. *Jurnal IHSAN: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.61104/ihsan.v1i2.57>
- Bayu, F. (2022). Kajian tentang Efektivitas Pesan dalam Komunikasi. *Jurnal ilmiah idea*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.36085/idea.v1i2.4807>

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

- Budhi Pamungkas Gautama, Yuliawati, A. K., Nurhayati, N. S., Fitriyani, E., & Pratiwi, I. I. (2020). Pengembangan Desa Wisata melalui Pendekatan Pemberdayaan Masyarakat. *BERNAS: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 1(4). <https://doi.org/10.31949/jb.v1i4.414>
- Cahyono, A. S. (2016). Pengaruh media sosial terhadap perubahan sosial masyarakat di Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial & Ilmu Politik* Diterbitkan Oleh Fakultas Ilmu Sosial & Politik, Universitas Tulungagung, 9(1).
- Cangara Hafied. (2020). *Perencanaan & Strategi Komunikasi*. Rajawali Pers.
- Firmansyah, F., Budiman, A., Adilansyah, A., Muhamadong, M., & Nur, M. (2023). Partisipasi Masyarakat Dalam Pelaksanaan Musyawarah Perencanaan Pembangunan (Musrembang) Desa. *JISIP (Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Pendidikan)*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.58258/jisip.v7i1.4502>
- Hamsa Ramadhan, A., Mulyani, S., Vana Hafizah, C., & Ar Rahman, M. A. A. R. (2022). Sistem Pembelajaran Berbasis Terknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi. *Edumaspul: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.33487/edumaspul.v6i1.2286>
- Hastrida, A., & Hendriyani. (2023). Pengaruh Komunikasi Dialogis terhadap Kepercayaan pada Pemerintah. *Jurnal Studi Komunikasi Dan Media*, 27(2). <https://doi.org/10.17933/jskm.2023.5144>
- Iman, N., & Rahmat, D. (2020). Strategi Komunikasi Kepala Desa dalam Meningkatkan Kesadaran Bergotong Royong. *Jurnal ATSAR UNISA*, 1, 77–84.
- Juniasa, I. D. N. (2020). Dampak Kebijakan Pembangunan Pariwisata Pantai Terhadap Apsek Sosial, Ekonomi, Dan Perilaku Masyarakat. *Jurnal Sains Sosio Humaniora*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.22437/jssh.v4i2.11551>
- Krisnanti, P. J., Widiantara, I. K. A., & Sutana, I. G. (2022). Strategi Komunikasi Pembangunan Pemerintah Desa Giri Emas Dalam Pengembangan Desa Wisata Di Tengah Pandemi Covid-19. *Paper Knowledge . Toward a Media History of Documents*, 3(April), 49–58.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, M. (1994). *Qualitative Data Analysis An Expanded Sourcebook*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Muchammad Satrio Wibowo, & Belia, L. A. (2023). Partisipasi Masyarakat Dalam Pengembangan Pariwisata Berkelanjutan. *Jurnal Manajemen Perhotelan Dan Pariwisata*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.23887/jmpp.v6i1.58108>
- Mustanir, A., Sellang, K., Ali, A., Madaling, M., & Mutmainna, M. (2018). Peranan Aparatur Pemerintah Desa Dan Partisipasi Masyarakat Dalam Musyawarah Perencanaan Pembangunan Di Desa Tonrongnge Kecamatan Baranti Kabupaten Sidenreng Rappang. *Jurnal Ilmiah Clean Government (JCG)*, 2(1).
- Nadia, H. (2023). *Public Relations dalam Era Digital : Menghadapi Tantangan dan Peluang Baru*. ResearchGate, 1(1).
- Nida, F. L. K. (2014). Persuasi dalam media komunikasi massa. *Jurnal Komunikasi Penyiaran Islam “AT-TABSIR”*, 2(2).
- Putra Perssela, R., Mahendra, R., & Rahmadiani, W. (2022). Pemanfaatan Media Sosial untuk Efektivitas Komunikasi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Kuliah Kerja Nyata (JIMAKUKERTA)*, 2(3). <https://doi.org/10.36085/jimakukerta.v2i3.4525>
- Rafi, K. A., & Sumarlan, I. (2025). Strategi Komunikasi Inovatif Dalam Mempromosikan Ideologi Islam Berkemajuan: Pendekatan Muhammadiyah. *SIBATIK JOURNAL: Jurnal Ilmiah Bidang Sosial*, 4(8). <https://www.publish.ojs-indonesia.com>
- Rahartri. (2019). “Whatsapp” Media Komunikasi Efektif Masa Kini (Studi Kasus Pada Layanan Jasa Informasi Ilmiah di Kawasan Puspipetek). *Visi Pustaka*.
- Rahma, F. A., Harjono, H. S., & Sulisty, U. (2023). Problematika Pemanfaatan Media Pembelajaran Berbasis Digital. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.31004/basicedu.v7i1.4653>
- Rusandi, & Muhammad Rusli. (2021). Merancang Penelitian Kualitatif Dasar/Deskriptif dan Studi Kasus. *Al-Ubudiyah: Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Studi Islam*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.55623/au.v2i1.18>
- Safitri, B., & Mujahid, N. S. (2024). Komunikasi Efektif dalam Organisasi. *Cendekia Inovatif Dan Berbudaya*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.59996/cendib.v1i3.318>
- Sumarlan, I., & Anis, E. Z. (2025). Strategic Communication in Religious Media: A Study of Muhammadiyah Digital Public Relations through www. suaramuhammadiyah. id. *Al-I’lam: Jurnal Komunikasi Dan Penyiaran Islam*, 8(2), 52–62.
- Sumarlan, I., Muktiyo, W., Pawito, P., & Rahmanto, A. N. (2025). Public relations strategies in religious organizations: a qualitative study of Muhammadiyah’s organizational communication. *Frontiers in Communication*, 10(July), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomm.2025.1574048>
- Syarifuddin, & Utari, E. D. (2022). *Media Pembelajaran (Dari Masa Konvensional Hingga Masa Digital)*. Bening Media Publishing, 18(1).
- Wiyanto. (2011). *Pengelolaan Komplain(Keluhan) Masyarakat Dalam Mewujudkan Tata Pamong Yang Baik (Good*

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES OF VILLAGE GOVERNMENT IN MANAGING CONFLICTS OVER BEACH ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES

Hamdan Febrian Ilham Yahya and Iman Sumarlan

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